

Students' ICT Use Preference and Comprehension Strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education: A Mixed Method Design

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Abstract. This study explored the significant relationship between students' ICT use preference and comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education. In this study, the researcher selected 150 senior high school students in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City as the study's respondents in the quantitative phase. In comparison, 10 students were selected for IDI and FGD in the qualitative phase. A mixed-method research design using an explanatory sequential approach was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean and Pearson-r Correlation Analysis. Findings revealed that students' ICT use preference and comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City were rated as moderately extensive. Correlation analysis proved a significant relationship between students' ICT use preference and comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education. The thematic analysis confirmed the moderately extensive ratings on students' ICT use preference and comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education. Thematic analysis showed that the reasons, enhanced understanding, balanced approach, and adaptation to varying topics confirmed the significant relationship between students' ICT use preference and comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education. The study, therefore, was conducted further to utilize findings through publication in a reputable research journal.

KEY WORDS

1. Teaching Home Economics 2. students' ICT use preference

3. comprehension strategies in TLE 4. explanatory sequential approach

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1. Introduction

The importance of ICT use preference and comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) lies in their ability to enhance the learning experience, improve students' understanding of TLE content, and prepare them for successful careers in various vocational and technical fields. ICT tools and resources encourage active engagement with TLE content. Students can interact with simulations, conduct research, and participate in online discussions, fostering deeper understanding and practical application of concepts. Also, ICT use preferences and comprehension strategies are essential in TLE as they empower students to actively engage with content, access diverse learning resources, personalize their learning experiences, develop practical skills, and enhance problem-solving abilities. They pre-

pare students for successful careers and lifelong learning, making TLE education more relevant and impactful. Several studies indicated that there exist a link between students' ICT use preferences and comprehension strategies in Technological and Livelihood Education. For instance, Granito and Chernobilsky (2012) showed that ICT use preferences have the potential to shape and enhance students' comprehension strategies in TLE by providing access to diverse resources, interactive learning opportunities, personalized learning experiences, and practical skills development. Also, Frydrychova Klimova and Poulova (2014) pointed out that students with a preference for extensive ICT use may have access to a wider range of digital resources, including online tutorials, videos, simulations, and interactive modules. Likewise, Francis (2017) showed that ICT preferences for interactive learning may encourage students to engage with online discussion forums, collaborative platforms, and real-time feedback mechanisms. As pointed out by Meel (2016), students' ICT preference use or the individual choices and inclinations of students when it comes to their utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools and resources in the context of their education. According to Kutluca (2014), students with a moderate preference typically acquire digital literacy and competence without becoming overly dependent on technology, which can serve them well in various educational and professional settings. This indicates a balanced approach to avoiding excessive screen time and digital distraction, which can be particularly beneficial in maintaining focus and productivity. Mahajan (2016) reported that students with a moderate preference use technology as a complementary tool to traditional methods. This balanced approach allows them to benefit from the advantages of both digital and analog learning. As described by Moskovsky et al. (2013), comprehension strategies is the various cognitive and metacognitive techniques

and approaches that students employ to understand and make sense of the information, content, and materials they encounter in their learning and educational experiences. As pointed out by Varga (2017), students actively engage with content, demonstrating critical thinking by asking questions, making connections, and evaluating the quality and credibility of information. They employ both inferential and deductive reasoning when faced with ambiguous or challenging content, seeking to uncover hidden meanings and patterns. More so, Maulana et al. (2013) pointed out that moderate preference students engage in metacognitive reflection, evaluating their own understanding and adjusting their comprehension strategies as needed. However, Kuzu et al. (2014) reported that a low level of students' comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) can have several consequences that may hinder their learning and development in this field. Without effective comprehension strategies, students may find it challenging to apply what they have learned in practical, real-world situations, which is a central aspect of TLE. Adding more, Oxford (2013) viewed that TLE often involves problem-solving and critical thinking. A low level of comprehension strategies can hinder students' ability to analyze and solve real-world problems effectively. Moreover, Runjic et al. (2015) noted that difficulty in understanding TLE content may lead to frustration and disengagement from the subject. Students may lose interest in TLE if they continually struggle to comprehend the material. While existing research may examine the immediate effects of students' ICT use preference on comprehension strategies, there might be limited exploration of the long-term impact. A research gap could involve conducting a mixed-method study to understand how these preferences and strategies evolve and affect students' career success in TLE fields. Thus, it is in this context that the researcher felt the need to fill in the research

gap by conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Cluster Public Secondary Schools in Davao City, using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher used descriptive correlational design to have a better understanding of the role of ICT use preference as a predictor of comprehension strategies of students, which is found to be scarce. Through surveying grade 7-10 students in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City, this study sought to explore the relationship between these variables which may serve as basis for intervention programs and enhance practices in the field of teaching.

1.1. *Theoretical/Conceptual Framework*—

The study is anchored on the proposition of Granito and Chernobilsky (2012) showed that ICT use preferences have the potential to shape and enhance students' comprehension strategies in TLE by providing access to diverse resources, interactive learning opportunities, personalized learning experiences, and practical skills development. Francis (2017) affirmed that ICT preferences for interactive learning may encourage students to engage with online discussion forums, collaborative platforms, and real-time feedback mechanisms. Such platforms can promote peer learning, where students share their comprehension strategies and help one another understand complex TLE concepts. In supports, Frydrychova Klimova and Poulova (2014) postulated that students with a preference for extensive ICT use may have access to a wider range of digital resources, including online tutorials, videos, simulations, and interactive modules. This increased access allows students to employ a broader array of comprehension strategies, such as watching instructional videos, conducting research online, and participating in virtual simulations. Moreover, a pragmatic paradigm was applied in this study. It aims to identify the problem and view it within its broadest context. As a pragmatist, the researcher adheres to a pragmatic worldview in which the creation of

individual realities is treated as a derivative of varying personal experiences and ideas encountered and not of an absolute default (Maddux Donnett, 2015). Through pragmatic exploration, an optimum answer was provided, as facts and accuracy may differ cross-wise between and among people, places, and periods. Furthermore, the researcher, like Terrell (2012), did not focus on issues and approaches by using only one method; rather, she embraced the pragmatic paradigm, which involves mixing data collection methods and data analysis procedures within the research processes (Creswell, 2013). The study's primary concern is the emphasis on initiatives that have meaningful consequences in solving learning issues, particularly desire for academic recognition among students in technology and livelihood education. Furthermore, this pragmatic approach is intended to design the research process, including all phases necessary for the theoretical underpinning of data collection and analysis. Hence, it can be deduced from the above that the philosophical worldview of things is vital to the meaning of research methodology. As shown in Figure 1, the study was composed of two variables. The independent variable is the ICT use Preference or the individual choices and inclinations of students when it comes to their utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools and resources in the context of their education. The measures of ICT use Preference according to Saricoban (2013) are affective component or the aspect of students' inclination and choices related to Information and Communication Technology (ICT) usage based on their sensory perceptions and how they perceive and interact with digital tools and resources; perceived usefulness or the choices and inclinations of students concerning their utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) based on the practicality and utility of technology in their educational endeavors; perceived control or the level of control and

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

autonomy that students prefer to have over the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools and resources they use for their educational purposes; and behavioural intention or the students' attitude and inclination towards their intended use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools and resources in their educational endeavors. The dependent variable is comprehension strategies or the various cognitive and metacognitive techniques and approaches that students employ to understand and make sense of the information, content, and materials they encounter in their learning and educational experiences. The measures of com-

prehension strategies according to Kubischta (2014) are self-efficacy or the strategies and techniques students employ to understand, process, and retain information in their learning activities; intrinsic value or the techniques and approaches students employ to understand and make sense of the information and concepts specific to the field of TLE; cognitive strategy or the mental techniques and approaches students employ to understand and make sense of the specific content and concepts within the field of TLE; and self-regulation or techniques and approaches students employ to manage and monitor their own learning in the context of TLE.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher employed mixed methods, specifically explanatory sequential research design. This is an evolving research technique that promotes the systematic synthesis or mixing of quantitative and qualitative data within a single study or ongoing investigation or inquiry (Creswell, 2013). This method collects and analyzes both quantitative and qualitative data and integrates data during data collection, analysis, and discussion. This method uses procedures that implement quantitative and qualitative components concurrently (Creswell, 2017). According to West (2012), in sequential explanatory design, the qualitative data helps explain or build on the initial quantitative results in the explanatory sequential method. The explanatory sequential approach is a two-phase mixed methods design that explains and enriches the quantitative findings; thus, it elaborates the quantitative results by collecting qualitative data from participants chosen from the respondents of the quantitative phase. Sometimes, there are insufficient arguments that quantitative or qualitative may not be resolved by it, and sometimes each provides different pictures (Creswell, 2017). In the quantitative phase, the researcher specifically used the correlational technique of research to gather data ideas, facts and information related to the study. descriptive-correlational research, according to Myers and Well (2013), examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause-and-effect relationships between variables. In this study, the use of descriptive-correlational was appropriate because the researcher only focused on the behavioral aspect of the respondents, and the researcher was unable to experiment with a controlled set-up. In this study, the researcher looked into the relationship between two variables— ICT use preference and students' comprehension strategies in technology and livelihood education. In the qualitative phase, the researcher used a phenomenological approach. A phenomenological study describes the ordinary meaning for several individuals of their lived experiences of a concept or phenomenon and focuses on their everyday experiences (Creswell, 2013). Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Phenomenology is the most appropriate approach because the researcher wants to understand students' lived experiences in Cluster 1 Public secondary schools in Davao City (Creswell, 2017). Moreover, the quantitative data based on the survey questionnaires on ICT use preference and students' comprehension strategies in technology and livelihood education was first collected and followed by the qualitative data based on the focus group discussion (FGD) and in-depth interview (IDI). This means a more dynamic and absolute understanding is possible than using only one data source alone (Creswell, 2013). Likewise, this method was used to compare, confirm, cross-validate, or corroborate findings, equally prioritizing the quantitative method. The researcher analyzed the survey data quantitatively and the FGD and IDI qualitatively to determine if the qualitative findings elaborated the quantitative findings (Creswell, 2013). Hence, this design was appropriate for purposely supplementing one method with the strengths of another (Creswell, 2013). Specifically, the quantitative component involved descriptive and correlational approaches.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—Quantitative Phase. The study's respondents were the Grade 7 students in Cluster 1, Davao City. The 155 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique in this study. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. In this study, specific inclusion criteria was implemented in determining the study's respondents. The primary consideration of this study is to choose respondents who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. The inclusion criteria are as follows: bonafide grade 7 students who are enrolled for S.Y. 2022-2023 in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City; students who are actively enrolled in TLE courses, as they are more likely to have relevant experiences and preferences related to TLE content; students who have access to ICT resources, such as computers, tablets, or the internet, to ensure they can effectively engage with ICT in their TLE studies; and who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions, and thus, it did not consider the school performance ratings of the students. Qualitative Phase. The researcher purposively selected 10 students for the in-depth interview (IDI) and 7 for the focus

group discussion (FGD). A total of 17 Grade 7 students in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City were invited as participants. It was also considered that the numbers of males and females were well represented. Purposive sampling was apt for the qualitative participant selection of this study because, according to Daymon and Holloway (2011), it was a technique wherein a sample was chosen based on their particular features or characteristics, which enables detailed exploration and understanding of the constructs under the study and research questions. As Miles et al. (2014) denoted, purposive sampling is well suited to in-depth qualitative studies.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—Two sets of instruments were used in this study: one for the quantitative phase and one for the qualitative phase. A panel of experts subjected these questionnaires to content validity and underwent pilot testing to test their validity and reliability. The experts' comments, corrections, and suggestions were incorporated into the final revisions of the questionnaires. Quantitative Phase. In the quantitative phase, the researcher employed the researcher-made questionnaires to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The first part was about ICT use preference indicated by the perceptual component, practicality, command, and behavioral intention. The modified questionnaire obtained a Cronbach alpha value of 0.954, interpreted as excellent, denoting the high reliability of the instrument. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use of the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of ICT use preference, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

The second part of the instrument was about the comprehension strategies of students. The questionnaire measured self-efficacy, intrinsic

value, cognitive strategy use, and self-regulation. The modified questionnaire obtained a Cronbach alpha value of 0.978, which was inter-

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation of ICT Use Preference

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The preference for ICT use by students is always observed.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The preference for ICT use by students is oftentimes observed.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The preference for ICT use by students is sometimes observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The preference for ICT use by students is seldom observed.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The preference for ICT use by students is never observed.

preted as excellent, denoting the high reliability of the instrument. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use of the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of

skills in using motivated learning strategies of the students, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Qualitative Phase. Using a semi-structured interview, the researcher conducted an IDI and FGD with 17 technology and livelihood students. The use of the semi-structured approach was essential to discover new themes that emerged during the interview. As Bryman and Bell (2011) described, is flexible and less rigid than structured. The researcher made an interview guide composed of open-ended questions to probe the participants’ lived ex-

periences with regard to ICT use preference and students’ comprehension strategies in technology and livelihood education. Also, the researcher probed how these experiences shape their beliefs, attitudes, and commitment toward learning. This interview guide had undergone content validation by three experts in the field of education. Their comments, corrections, and suggestions were incorporated into the final revisions of the questionnaires.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The researcher undertook the steps in conducting the study after validating the research questionnaire. Quantitative Phase Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Gradu-

ate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school’s division superintendent and then to the school principals of the selected public sec-

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation of Comprehension Strategies

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The comprehension strategies of students are always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The comprehension strategies of students are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The comprehension strategies of students are sometimes manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The comprehension strategies of students are seldom manifested.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The comprehension strategies of students are never manifested.

ondary schools in Cluster 1, Davao City. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. After the approval to conduct the study, the researcher proceeded to distribute the research instrument to the respondents. The study was conducted last June 21-25, 2023. Upon the distribution of the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents. More so, the respondents were given enough testing time for the questionnaires to be finished. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After that, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS. Qualitative Phase For the qualitative data collection, IDI and FGD were conducted to gather the participants' lived experiences regarding ICT use preference and students' comprehension strategies in technology and livelihood education after the invited

participants had emailed back the signed ICF. Regarding the conduct of the IDI and FGD, the researcher reflected in the ICF that the process had to be recorded. Only those invited participants who could email back their signed ICF were scheduled to join the IDI and FGD. Also, the researcher ensured that her time schedule was most convenient for the participants. Using the validated open-ended questionnaire, she had to limit the IDI and FGD sessions to 30 to 40 minutes. In addition, she thoroughly discussed the ethical considerations with the participants. Also, the participants' perspectives on the phenomenon of interest were revealed according to how they viewed it, not as the researcher viewed it. Also, since the interview involved a personal interaction where cooperation was essential (Creswell, 2013), the researcher who acted as the interviewer saw that she had a good rapport with the interviewees by using a non-threatening stance during the IDI. Likewise, for the FGD, the researcher sent an email or text through messenger to confirm the availability

of the participants who signed up to join the FGD at the time scheduled for the FGD Google Meet session. An invite was emailed at least two days before the scheduled FGD session. The researcher acted as the facilitator during the FGD and stimulated the discussion or brain-

storming through sensibly chosen guide statements, which were prepared beforehand and validated by a panel of experts. Participants in the FGD were informed prior to the submission of the signed ICF that the whole session would be recorded.

2.5. Trustworthiness of the Study—To establish the study's trustworthiness, the researcher followed Lincoln and Guba's (1985) four proposed criteria for evaluating interpretive research work: credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. This study's trustworthiness was addressed through thorough data collection by survey and in-depth interviews, supported by FGD for triangulation. **Credibility** To ensure the credibility of this study, the researcher adopted a well-established research method. The researcher recognized the importance of incorporating correct operational measures for the concept that was being studied. Credibility was achieved by ensuring that the source of the data was credible. The researcher also ensured the honesty of the participants by giving them a chance to refuse to participate in the study. Also, the researcher ensured the quality of this study by carefully adhering to the protocols set by the Rizal Memorial Colleges Graduate School; the process flow in data collection, data analysis, and data integration were carefully reviewed, ensuring quality and dependability.

Transferability The researcher addressed transferability by providing readers with evidence that the research findings could apply to other contexts, situations, times, and populations. Transferability is concerned with the extent to which the study's findings can be applied to other situations (Creswell, 2013). The readers had to note the specific details of the situations and methods to compare them to a similar situation familiar to them.

Dependability To address the dependability

issue more directly, the researcher made sure that the process within the study was discussed in detail, thereby enabling future researchers to repeat the work, if not necessarily to gain the same results or findings of the study. In order for the readers to gain a thorough understanding of the methods and their effectiveness, the researcher included sections such as the research design and its implementation, described what was planned, and how they were executed on a strategic level. The researcher described the operational details of data collection, addressed the details of what has to be done in the field, and provided a reflective appraisal of the project, evaluated the appropriateness of the process of the inquiry that was being undertaken. With the guidance of her mentor and evaluation of the expert panelists, all activities were done properly; as a result, stakeholders and the readers can be assured of the study's dependability.

Confirmability To safeguard the accuracy of the transcription and initial interpretation of the data, IDIs, and FGD were recorded, and the transcriptions were subjected to the review of the participant's responses. The process included in Creswell's (2017) steps and procedures in analyzing qualitative data is known as the last stage in validating the accuracy of the information; through this method, the researcher assured confirmability of the study's findings (Creswell, 2017). As such, the researcher used an audit trail of raw data, analysis notes, process notes, personal notes, and preliminary developmental information to achieve confirmability. In other words, the researcher's findings were derived from the survey responses and narratives

of the participants in the IDI and FGD.

2.6. *Ethical Considerations*—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study, following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. Social Value Research is an integral part of societal development, and this particular study emphasizes the social value associated with teacher collaboration and motivation, specifically among elementary school teachers. A pressing social issue that interests me is how their teachers' efficacy influences students' digital text reading and comprehension. The findings from this study could inform educational authorities, enabling them to create effective programs and policies that directly benefit students. The researcher prioritizes social value as a crucial component of ethical research, reflecting the anticipated benefits a research intervention can provide to the community. Ethical considerations in research are vital in ensuring that the rights and welfare of participants are protected. Among the significant ethical challenges are ensuring participant anonymity, avoiding the collection of identifiable personal information, and safeguarding the identities of those involved in the study. By addressing these moral issues, researchers can uphold the integrity of their work while contributing positively to society. Moreover, ethical research practices promote trust and transparency, encouraging stakeholder participation and collaboration. By adhering to ethical guidelines, the research can foster a supportive environment where findings can lead to meaningful improvements in educational practices and ultimately enhance student learning outcomes. The commitment to eth-

ical considerations protects the participants and ensures the validity and reliability of the research outcomes, thereby maximizing the potential social impact. Informed Consent The researcher obtained the consent of respondents through written informed consent. They were adequately informed about the purpose of the study and given ample explanations so that they could better understand the reason for their participation and choose whether to participate or not. It was made clear that respondents' involvement in the study was voluntary. If they ever refused to participate, the researcher did not force them to do so. Besides, the researcher was cautious in ensuring the respondents' psychological well-being. Written permission was secured from the respondents. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to study the factors that hinder/promote students' comprehension strategies as determined by ICT use preference and may contribute to their enhancement.

Vulnerability of Research Participants The study's respondents are junior high school students, so they are considered vulnerable since they are not yet of legal age. They are also considered highly vulnerable psychologically. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed.

Privacy and Confidentiality This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2012, wherein the researcher assured that the data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the real source of information, to protect the participants' identities. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the respondents' consent. Thus, access was limited to the researcher alone to ensure that no personal data would be exposed. To protect the privacy of the respondents, it was assured that the researcher was the only person who could access the data on the survey. After

the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently disposed of all the survey questionnaires and deleted the data results to ensure that data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the real source of information.

Risk, Benefits, and Safety In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and thoroughly and adequately explained the purpose and benefits of the study and the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the survey questionnaire. Without restrictions, the respondents could ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not subjected to harm in any way whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire and interview guide used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the study's respondents. Since the informants are in grade 7 and considered minors so, the researcher requested the parents and the teachers to help them understand the interview and assist them during the course of the interview. Likewise, this study was designed purely to collect academic information related to the study, and they were not asked for personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher ensured that the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire. The respondents were given the freedom not to answer questions that made them feel any psychological or emotional distress, and they would be free to withdraw as respondents to the study if they thought that they could not discuss the information that was being asked of them. The researcher valued their participation and placed their welfare as the highest priority during the study.

Justice To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all respondents equally regardless of whether they would be respondents in the survey. The researcher was not prejudiced in selecting the respondents for the study—anybody who qualified to be en-

rolled in the purposively selected schools. During the study, the researcher respected the respondents by interrupting their routine as little as possible. To compensate for the time spent during data gathering, the researcher gave tokens of appreciation to the respondents. This token was an assortment of souvenirs. The tokens were sent via courier and sealed carefully in a package. Also, each token was sanitized before being sent to your doorstep.

Transparency To provide transparency in this study, any communication about the research was done honestly and openly. To safeguard the respondents' welfare, the researcher correctly implemented the methods discussed in this study. All the necessary documents that supported the data analysis were included. Notably, the researcher described the extent of the respondents' involvement in this study and shared how the researcher-maintained objectivity in analyzing data and presenting the study's results.

Qualification of the Researcher

The researcher ensured that other factors like the conflict of interest did not influence the respondents' responses. However, since the information was minor, their parent's assistance and teachers' support were advised during the interview. The study's findings could be accessed by the respondent's parents and school administrators of the participating schools because the information would be made available as long as they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the success of the In the study, the Division of Davao City was given a furnished copy of the research results so that the respondents could access them and use them for learning and further study.

Adequacy of Facilities

The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and ample and available learning materials. The study was conducted within the time set by the researcher.

The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by adequately encoding the respondents' ratings during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results were proficient and aligned, serving as a primary basis for adequacy.

Community Involvement It was good practice to involve the community during every research phase, from planning to reporting.

2.7. Data Analysis—Quantitative Phase
The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the ICT use preference and students' comprehension strategies in technology and livelihood education in Cluster 1, Davao City. Pearson-r Analysis. It was applied to evaluate the influence of knowledge ICT use preference on students' comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. Qualitative Strand The data from the IDI and FGD were analyzed using thematic analysis. The interview was recorded so that the data and notes obtained could be analyzed to determine the emerging codes and themes. This method emphasizes pinpointing, examining, and recording patterns or themes within data. Themes are patterns across data sets that are important to the description of a phenomenon and are associated with a specific research question (Mertens, 2018). In the thematic analysis, the researcher first read and re-read the transcripts to become familiar with the data. The data were organized to generate initial codes. Codes reduced ideas into smaller chunks of meaning. Codes were examined and grouped according to themes. Themes were formed, reviewed, modified, and developed. The themes were coherent and distinctive from each other. Lastly, the themes were defined to determine their meaning (Creswell, 2017). After the data

Hence, the researcher planned to share the findings generated with the community and community involvement was accorded primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate methods to apply in their context, and use of the results or findings. The findings of this study would then be shared with the community through gatherings, fora, and conferences.

collection, a detailed step was applied to analyze the data.

*2.8. Sequence, Emphasis, And Mixing Procedures—*This study employed a sequential collection of quantitative and qualitative components. However, the data integration happens during the analysis and interpretation phase. Sequence. A sequential-explanatory mixed-method design was used in this study. This means that the data gathered in the quantitative strand was further verified in the qualitative strand to explain the salient results of the survey. For the quantitative strand, the researcher collected the data online through adapted questionnaires and interviews of Grade 7 in Cluster 1 schools in Davao City with a validated interview guide for the qualitative phase. This means that the survey and interview were conducted separately and simultaneously. The qualitative data verified the quantitative data for cross-validation or confirmation of findings. With this method, the qualitative results determine the depth of the study's quantitative findings. Emphasis. The quantitative data were given more emphasis in the study because they used empirical tools and provided substantive support for the qualitative findings. The findings were integrated during the interpretation phase of the study. The sequential-explanatory design framework shows two strands, with data collection and analysis from the quantitative and qualitative strands. By mixing both quantitative

and qualitative research and data, the researcher gained an in-depth understanding after corroboration while offsetting the weaknesses inherent in using each approach by itself. Mixing Procedures. Given the two separate phases, the design required a substantial amount of time to complete all data collection. The primary purpose of mixing quantitative and qualitative data is for the qualitative data to help explain the quantitative data. Thus, quantitative and qualitative data were connected. Mixed methodologies were observed when formulating the purpose, research questions, and data integration in the study's findings and interpretation. A data integration technique was applied to establish either the complementation of quantitative and qualitative data or the sequential connection between these data sets. The qualitative data either confirms or contrasts the quantitative findings. Neither of these citations of the previous studies explained the results. In addition, the specific research questions of the survey served as a guide in interpreting the results. The mixing was done to understand better the influence of knowledge ICT use preference on students' comprehension strategies in technology and livelihood education. A sequential-explanatory mixed methods design was used, where quantitative and qualitative data were corroborated to determine the influence of knowledge ICT use preference on students' comprehension strategies in tech-

nology and livelihood education in Cluster 1, Davao City. Then, after giving adequate time, the responses to the survey questionnaires were conducted using Google Forms, which were encoded and analyzed. Concurrently, IDI and FGD were conducted in the selected secondary public schools. In the quantitative strand, computer applications analyzed the participants' responses to the validated survey questionnaire, and the answers were output as numeric data. In addition, appropriate statistical tools, including mean and Pearson-r analysis, were used to analyze the quantitative data. In the qualitative data strand, the researcher purposefully selected the participants for the IDI and FGD. The schedule of the IDI and FGD was set at the participants' convenience. Every detail of the responses was taken into consideration, but those that were not relevant to the study were not reflected. In addition, the interview proceedings were recorded with the participant's consent. Thematic analysis was employed, consisting of six phases. The researcher started by transcribing, reading, and re-reading the data, and then initial codes or features of the data were created. The next phase was searching for the themes and collating the codes. As to integrating the quantitative and qualitative results phases, the researcher interpreted and explained the quantitative and qualitative results to arrive at a very substantial discussion, implications, and recommendations.

3. Results and Discussion

This reflects the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of findings. Specifically, this chapter reveals quantitative and qualitative data relevant to addressing the research questions formulated in Chapter 1. The tabulated quantitative findings are presented in Tables 1-3, while qualitative findings are presented in Tables 4-5.

3.1. Students' ICT Use Preference in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City— Table 1 summarizes the students' ICT use preference in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. It shows that students' overall

mean ICT use preference is 3.39, which is described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed among the respondents. More so, the ICT use preference of students in terms of perceptual components acquired the

highest mean score of 3.43, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. In contrast, the ICT use preference of students in terms of command got the lowest mean score of 3.21, which is described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes followed by the Grade 7 students. The result implies that students exhibit a balanced and well-considered approach to integrating technology into their learning. This level of preference suggests that while students are comfortable and open to using ICT in their education, they do not exclusively rely on technology or ultimately reject it. This supports the findings of Kutluca (2014) that students with a moderate preference typ-

ically acquire digital literacy and competence without becoming overly dependent on technology, which can serve them well in various educational and professional settings. This indicates a balanced approach to avoiding excessive screen time and digital distraction, which can be particularly beneficial in maintaining focus and productivity. More so, these findings support the idea of Mahajan (2016) that students with a moderate preference use technology as a complementary tool to traditional methods. This balanced approach allows them to benefit from the advantages of both digital and analog learning.

Table 1. Summary of Students’ ICT Use Preference in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Perceptual Component	3.43	Extensive
Practicality	3.41	Extensive
Command	3.21	Moderately Extensive
Behavioral Intention	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.39	Moderately Extensive

Meanwhile, the table shows that the ICT use preference in terms of perceptual component was assessed by the Grade 7 students as extensive with a category mean of 3.43, interpreted as oftentimes observed. The mean rating of the different items, as shown in Appendix A, ranges from 2.38 to 4.20. On the one hand, the item Never hesitating to use a computer because I look bright and intelligent (refer to Appendix A) has a mean rating of 2.38, described as less extensive and interpreted as seldom observed by the respondents. On the other hand, being confident that I can handle a computer without damaging it (refer to Appendix A) reflects a mean of 4.20, described as very extensive and

interpreted as always observed by the respondents.

3.2. *Students’ Comprehension Strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City*— Table 2 summarizes students’ comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. As shown in the table, students’ comprehension strategies obtained an overall mean score of 3.31 with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the Grade 7 students. Adding more, results in Table 2 show that students’ comprehension strategies in Tech-

nology and Livelihood Education in terms of intrinsic value acquired the highest mean score of 3.42, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested. In contrast, students' comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in terms of effectiveness acquired the lowest mean score of 3.19, which is moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the Grade 7 students. This means that students utilize a balanced and pragmatic set of cognitive and metacognitive approaches to comprehend and make meaning of the information they encounter. This supports the findings of Varga (2017) that students actively engage with content, demonstrating critical thinking by asking questions, making con-

nections, and evaluating the quality and credibility of information. They employ inferential and deductive reasoning when faced with ambiguous or challenging content, seeking to uncover hidden meanings and patterns. Additionally, the result is congruent with the view of Maulana et al. (2013) that moderate preference students engage in metacognitive reflection, evaluating their understanding and adjusting their comprehension strategies as needed. Moreover, the result supports the idea of Rimm-Kaufman and Sandilos (2013) that they value collaborative learning and discussion, using group interactions to deepen their comprehension and consider multiple perspectives.

Table 2. Students' Comprehension Strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Effectiveness	3.19	Moderately Extensive
Intrinsic Value	3.42	Extensive
Cognitive Strategy Use	3.21	Moderately Extensive
Autonomy	3.40	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.31	Moderately Extensive

Meanwhile, students' comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in terms of effectiveness were described by the respondents in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City as moderately extensive with a category mean of 3.19. This means that the students' comprehension strategy is sometimes observed. The mean rating of the different items, as shown in Appendix A, ranges from 2.57 to 4.13. Knowing I will be able to learn the material for this project (refer to Appendix A) shows a mean rating of 2.57, which is described as less extensive and interpreted as this item seldom observed by the students.

Further, the item Insuring I can do an excellent job on the problems and tasks assigned for this project (refer to Appendix A) has a mean rating of 4.13, described as extensive and interpreted as this item oftentimes manifested. This implies that students utilize a balanced set of reasonably effective strategies in their learning. It suggests that students are neither relying solely on efficient strategies nor exclusively using less effective ones. This supports Brown's (2014) idea that a moderate preference level indicates that students balance effort and outcomes. They are effective in their learning without overextending themselves. Moreover, the result agrees

with Mbatha's (2015) idea that students with a moderate level of comprehension strategies choose a mix of strategies that align with different content and learning contexts, demonstrating adaptability. They achieve decent learning outcomes as their chosen strategies help them understand and remember the material, even if they are not the most advanced techniques. Students' comprehension strategies of students in Technology and Livelihood Education in terms of intrinsic value as shown in Table 2 reflects as extensive category mean of 3.42 which means that it is sometimes manifested by the students. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items, as shown in Appendix A, ranges from 2.85 to 4.02. The table further reveals that the item Liking what I learn in the projects (refer to Appendix A) has a mean rating of 2.85 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as item sometimes manifested by the students. Meanwhile, the item Thinking that what we are learning in this class is interesting (refer to Appendix A) has mean rating of 4.02 described as extensive and interpreted as students' comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education is oftentimes manifested. This implies that the techniques and approaches students employ to understand and make sense of the information and concepts specific to the field of TLE is oftentimes manifested. This supports the idea of Wehe (2013) that comprehension strategies that hold intrinsic value for students in TLE are those that help them not only understand but also apply the acquired knowledge and skills to real-world scenarios. This is particularly important in TLE, where the focus is on preparing students for vocational or career-related pursuits. Adding more, this is congruent to the view of Wong (2014) that intrinsic comprehension strategies facilitate students in extracting meaningful lessons from their hands-on experiences, making their learning more valuable and practical.

3.3. Significant Relationship Between Students' ICT Use Preference and Comprehension Strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City—The results on the analysis on the relationship between students' ICT use preference and comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 3 shows that ICT use preference has a significant positive relationship with the students' comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .703$, $p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of ICT use preference changes, the extent of students' comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education also significantly changes. Moreover, the table also shows that the ICT use preference in terms of perceptual component; practicality; command; and behavioral intention are significantly correlated with students' comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education as evident on the correlation coefficient values of 0.602, 0.577, 0.545, and 0.705. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between students' ICT use preference and comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education. This implies that students who prefer ICT for efficient information retrieval may employ search strategies and digital tools to quickly access relevant TLE materials. This supports the proposition of Granito and Chernobilsky (2012) that ICT use preferences have the potential to shape and enhance students' comprehension strategies in TLE by providing access to diverse resources, interactive learning opportunities, personalized learning experiences, and practical skills development. This also supports the findings of

Francis (2017) that ICT preferences for interactive learning may encourage students to engage with online discussion forums, collaborative platforms, and real-time feedback mecha-

nisms. Such platforms can promote peer learning, where students share their comprehension strategies and help one another understand complex TLE concepts.

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between Students’ ICT Use Preference and Comprehension Strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

ICT Use Preference	r-value	p-value	Decision
Perceptual Component	0.602*	0.000	Reject H ₀
Practicality	0.577*	0.000	Reject H ₀
Command	0.545*	0.000	Reject H ₀
Behavioural Intention	0.705*	0.000	Reject H ₀
Overall Multicultural Instruction	0.703*	0.000	Reject H ₀

*Significant at p<0.05

3.4. *Standpoints of the Participants on the Quantitative Results Regarding the Extents of Students’ ICT Use Preference and Comprehension Strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education*—Table 4 presents the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the moderately extensive ratings on students’ ICT use preference and comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education. On the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the moderately extensive rating of students’ ICT use preference, there were three emerging reasons that identified namely: teacher guidance; social interaction; and diverse learning styles.

3.4.1. *Teacher Guidance*—Teacher guidance can provide structure and clear objectives for students using ICT. This can help students navigate the digital learning environment effectively. More so, teachers can tailor their guidance to individual students, providing personalized assistance as needed. This can enhance

the learning experience for each student. The result implies that some students appreciate the guidance and structure provided by teachers in a classroom setting. They believe that face-to-face instruction is essential for certain subjects or topics and prefer ICT as a supplementary tool rather than a primary means of learning. The result is congruent to Gilakjani and Leong (2012) that teacher guidance can help students strike a balance between traditional and technology-based learning methods, ensuring that both are used effectively. Teachers can track students’ progress more effectively when they are actively involved in guiding ICT use. This allows for timely interventions and adjustments in the learning process.

3.4.2. *Social Interaction*—A moderate level of social interaction through ICT can facilitate collaborative learning experiences. Students can work together on projects, discuss ideas, and share knowledge, which can enhance their understanding and retention of information. Social interaction can help students build rela-

tionships with peers, creating a sense of community and support within the digital learning environment. The result means that students value and seek interaction with their peers and instructors in their ICT-based learning. Still, they do not want this interaction to dominate or overwhelm their educational experience. Instead, they prefer a measured and purposeful level of social engagement that complements their learning goals while allowing them to maintain focus and avoid potential distractions. The result supports the view of Abedalaziz et al. (2013) that a moderate level of social interaction fosters a balanced learning experience. Students can benefit from the advantages of ICT, such as accessing resources and tools, while also having the opportunity to collaborate and learn from others. Students can engage in collaborative activities and discussions without it becoming the primary focus of their learning. This approach encourages meaningful and goal-oriented collaborations that enhance their understanding of the subject matter.

3.4.3. Diverse Learning Styles—A moderate level of social interaction indicates that students value and seek some level of interaction with their peers and instructors in their ICT-based learning, but they do not want this interaction to dominate or overwhelm their educational experience. Instead, they prefer a measured and purposeful level of social engagement that complements their learning goals while allowing them to maintain focus and avoid potential distractions. This indicates that students engage in collaborative activities and discussions without it becoming the primary focus of their learning. This approach encourages meaningful and goal-oriented collaborations that enhance their understanding of the subject matter. The result supports the assertion of that a moderate level of social interaction fosters a balanced learning experience. Students can benefit from the advantages of ICT, such as accessing resources and tools, while also having the opportunity

to collaborate and learn from others. Adding more, Amin (2014) affirmed that a moderate level of social interaction is adaptable, allowing students to choose when and how they engage with others. They have the flexibility to collaborate when it's most relevant and beneficial for their learning process. From the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the moderately extensive rating on students' comprehension strategies in technology and livelihood education, there were three emerging codes that were identified, namely: enhanced understanding, balanced approach, and adaptation to varying topics.

3.4.4. Enhanced Understanding—A moderate level of enhanced understanding on students' comprehension strategies in TLE means that students are using a combination of traditional and technology-driven methods to gain a comprehensive and profound understanding of TLE topics. They utilize a variety of strategies and tools to enhance their comprehension, fostering a holistic and adaptable learning experience. The result implies that students achieve a deeper level of comprehension and mastery of TLE concepts and skills, going beyond surface-level understanding to apply their knowledge effectively. The result is congruent to the view of Dörnyei and Kubanyiova (2014) that a moderate level of enhanced understanding ensures that students use a balanced learning approach, incorporating both traditional resources (e.g., textbooks, lectures) and technology-enhanced resources. Students are not only expected to understand TLE theory but also to apply their knowledge practically. The moderate approach fosters the ability to translate theory into real-world practice.

3.4.5. Balanced Approach—Balanced approach in students' comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education aims to ensure that students receive a well-rounded and adaptable education. It combines traditional and technology-driven methods to create a compre-

hensive and effective learning experience, fostering adaptability and problem-solving skills essential for success in TLE fields. The result means that students are using a combination of traditional learning resources such as textbooks, classroom instruction, and hands-on experiences, along with technology-based resources such as digital simulations, online tutorials, and interactive tools. The result supports Babae's (2012) proposition that students can maximize their learning potential by leveraging the benefits of both traditional and technology-enhanced resources, making their learning experience more effective and efficient. A balanced approach ensures that students achieve a thorough understanding of TLE topics, combining theoretical knowledge with practical skills for a more holistic comprehension.

3.4.6. *Adaptation to Varying Topics*— Adaptation to varying topics in TLE empowers students to become flexible and efficient learners. They learn to select and apply the most suitable strategies and resources for each TLE

topic, resulting in a deeper understanding, increased engagement, and greater readiness for diverse careers within the field of Technology and Livelihood Education. This indicates that students understand that TLE encompasses diverse subjects, from agriculture and culinary arts to information technology and engineering. They adapt their comprehension strategies to suit each TLE topic's specific requirements and challenges. This adaptability allows for a more focused, efficient, and contextually relevant approach to comprehension. The result supports the assertion of Peterson (2017) that a moderate level of adaptation empowers students to customize their comprehension strategies according to the subject matter. This results in more effective learning experiences tailored to the nuances of each TLE topic. The approach ensures that students perceive the relevance of their comprehension strategies to the specific topic they are studying, making it easier for them to connect theoretical knowledge to practical applications.

Table 4. Standpoints of the Participants on the Quantitative Results Regarding the Extents of Students' ICT Use Preference and Comprehension Strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education

Essential Theme	Reasons
Confirmed Moderately Extensive Rating on Students' ICT Use Preference	Teacher Guidance
	Social Interaction
	Diverse Learning Styles
Confirmed Moderately Extensive Rating on Students' Comprehension Strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education	Enhanced Understanding
	Balanced Approach
	Adaptation to Varying Topics

3.4.7. *Standpoints of the Participants on the Significant Relationship Between Students' ICT Use Preference and Comprehension Strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education*—Table 5 presents the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the significant relationship between students' ICT use preference and comprehension strategies in technology and livelihood education. There were three emerging codes that identified namely: enhanced resources access; interactive learning; and visual learning.

3.4.8. *Enhanced Resources Access*—Enhanced resources access empowers students to personalize their TLE learning experiences by selecting digital resources and ICT tools that align with their preferences and learning styles. This customization improves their comprehension strategies, as they engage with materials that resonate with their individual needs. The result implies that ICT provides students easy access to a wealth of resources, including digital textbooks, online tutorials, and multimedia materials. Students' comprehension improves significantly When they prefer these resources and incorporate them into their strategies. This supports the view of Piccinini and Scarantino (2016) that with improved access to digital resources, students can efficiently retrieve and utilize information, reducing the time and effort required for research and study. This efficiency enhances their comprehension strategies, allowing them to focus on understanding and applying TLE concepts more effectively. Enhanced access provides students with a wide array of digital learning materials, such as e-books, online courses, videos, and simulations.

3.4.9. *Interactive Learning*—Interactive learning involves students actively participating in the learning process, collaborating with peers, and engaging with digital content, simulations, or activities. It aligns with students'

ICT use preference when they choose and enjoy interactive tools and methods as part of their comprehension strategies in TLE. This implies that ICT tools often facilitate interactive and engaging learning experiences. Students who prefer and use such tools develop better comprehension strategies because they are more actively involved in the learning process. This supports the findings of Godzicki et al. (2013) that interactive learning encourages students to actively engage with the subject matter. When students prefer and utilize interactive ICT tools, their comprehension strategies become more focused on participatory and hands-on learning. ICT-based interactive learning often includes problem-solving exercises. When students choose these types of activities based on their preference, their comprehension strategies evolve to prioritize analytical and problem-solving skills.

3.4.10. *Visual Learning*—The implications of visual learning on the relationship between students' ICT use preference and comprehension strategies in TLE are significant. Students who prefer visual learning are likely to choose ICT tools rich in visual content, which enhances their understanding, retention, and ability to simplify complex ideas in TLE. This alignment supports effective learning and a practical approach to problem-solving and real-world application. The result implies that visual learners may prefer and benefit from ICT tools that present information in graphical and multimedia formats. This preference aligns with their comprehension strategies and contributes to a significant relationship. This supports the idea of Goodin (2012) that visual learning aligns with students' ICT use preference when they choose tools that provide visual content. This preference enhances comprehension strategies by leveraging visual aids, helping students understand complex TLE concepts more effectively.

Table 5. Standpoints of the Participants on the Significant Relationship Between Students’ ICT Use Preference and Comprehension Strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education

Essential Theme	Reasons
Confirmed Significant Relationship Between Students’ ICT Use Preference and Comprehension Strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education	Enhanced Resources Access
	Interactive Learning
	Visual Learning

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher’s conclusions and recommendations. The discussions were supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusions were in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—This study aimed to determine the significant relationship between students’ ICT use preference and comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City using mixed methods, specifically the sequential-explanatory design wherein adapted survey questionnaires were used in the quantitative phase and through in-depth interview (IDI) and focus group discussion (FGD) in the qualitative phase. On the one hand, in the quantitative phase of the study, adapted survey questionnaires were used to gather data from the students to determine the extent of ICT use preference and comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education. For the quantitative strand, the researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. In contrast, a semi-structured interview guide was

used in the qualitative strand. Based on the results, the summary of the findings was the following: Students’ ICT use preference in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City has an overall mean of 3.39 with a moderately extensive descriptive rating. Also, students’ ICT use preference in terms of perceptual component, practicality, command, and behavioral intention obtained mean scores of 3.43, 3.41, 3.21, and 3.23, respectively. Students’ comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City got an overall mean of 3.31 with moderately extensive descriptive rating. Also, students’ comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in terms of effectiveness; intrinsic value; cognitive strategy use; and autonomy obtained the mean scores of 3.19, 3.42, 3.21, and 3.40, respectively. ICT use preference has a significant positive relationship with the students’ comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in Clus-

ter 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .775$, $p < 0.05$). This means that as the preference for ICT use changes, students' comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education also change significantly. From the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the moderately extensive rating on ICT use preference, the three emerging reasons are teacher guidance, social interaction, and diverse learning styles. From the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the moderately extensive rating on students' comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education, the three emerging reasons are teacher guidance, social interaction, and diverse learning styles. The participants' standpoints on the quantitative results regarding the significant relationship between Students' ICT use preference and comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City are as follows: enhanced understanding, balanced approach, and adaptation to varying topics.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study and within the limitations and restrictions (such as the survey questionnaire and number of respondents), several conclusions are generated: Students' ICT use preference in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City was moderately extensive. Meanwhile, students' ICT use preference in terms of perceptual component and practicality obtained moderately extensive descriptive ratings, while students' ICT use preference in terms of command and behavioral intention was moderately extensive. The result implies that students exhibit a balanced and well-considered approach to integrating technology into their learning. Students' comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City were rated

as moderately extensive. Students' comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in terms of intrinsic value and autonomy belong to an extensive rating. In contrast, students' comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in terms of effectiveness and cognitive strategy use acquired a moderately extensive rating. This means that students utilize a balanced and pragmatic set of mental and metacognitive approaches to comprehend and make meaning of the information they encounter. Students' ICT use preference significantly correlates with the comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. Students who prefer ICT for efficient information retrieval may employ search strategies and digital tools to access relevant TLE materials quickly. The quantitative results on the moderately extensive students' ICT use preference were further substantiated by reasons (teacher guidance, social interaction, and diverse learning styles) that emerged during the thematic analysis of the qualitative data, generally confirming the results of the quantitative aspects of the study. The quantitative results on the moderately extensive comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education were further substantiated by reasons (teacher guidance, social interaction, and diverse learning styles) that emerged during the thematic analysis of the qualitative data, generally confirming the results of the quantitative aspects of the study. The quantitative results on the significant relationship between students' ICT use preference significant positive relationship with the comprehension strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education in Cluster 1 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City were further substantiated by reasons (enhanced understanding; balanced approach; and adaptation to varying topics) that emerged during the thematic analysis of the qualitative data, generally confirming the results of the quantitative aspects of the

study. The salient quantitative and qualitative findings revealed a parallel result. The corroborated finding means that the quantitative and qualitative findings merged and connected.

4.3. *Recommendations*—The Department of Education should create clear and comprehensive ICT policies that outline the integration of ICT into the TLE curriculum. These policies should address access, equity, and digital literacy. DepEd should invest in teacher training programs to enhance TLE educators' ICT skills and pedagogical approaches. Continuous professional development is key to improving instructional practices. School principals should establish mechanisms for monitoring the use of ICT in TLE classes and assess its impact on students' comprehension strategies. They should use this information to improve the program. In addition, they should ensure that ICT resources are available to all students, regardless of their

socio-economic background, and that accessible technologies are in place for students with disabilities. TLE Teachers should actively pursue professional development opportunities to improve ICT skills and stay current with technological advancements relevant to TLE. They should integrate ICT tools and platforms that reflect the real-world application of TLE content, providing students with hands-on experience. Students should engage in collaborative learning and knowledge-sharing through digital platforms and group projects. They should recognize the importance of continuous learning and adaptability in TLE fields and use ICT for self-improvement. Future researchers should investigate how cultural and contextual factors influence ICT use and comprehension strategies in TLE. They should also disseminate research findings to inform policy and practice, contributing to improving ICT integration in TLE.

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